

Moraea fugax Klipuintjie or Soetuintjie

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Importance:

An important traditional food source with potential as a wild crop, and crucial for understanding the variability within what is likely an undocumented species complex.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 128.17 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 29.5 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 6.31 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 61.2%, Duplicated: 38.4%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 1 744.42 kilobases

Contig number: 7 727

Sample Contributor contact details:

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Group: Monocot

Size: 50cm with a branched stem

Distribution:

Namaqualand southwards to the Cape Peninsula, and eastwards across the southern Cape as far as Swellendam.

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